

University and Eastern European Modernity: Role of the ‘Governmental University’ in the Modernization of Russian Empire, USSR and Post-Soviet Nations

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Abstract

In this short overview of the university’s history in Eastern Europe I tried to demonstrate the way traditional societies of this region transited into a condition of ambivalent modernity. Being in direct communication and under influence of modernization in the Western Europe, societies that were part of imperial Russia in the 19th century developed a highly ambivalent model of education and scientific institutions responsible for the rationalization of their cultures. A witness of this process, Aleksander Griboiedov call this modernity a «Drum Enlightenment» stressing upon the fact that the modernization was going on as an imperial policy imposed over traditional national cultures. The Eastern European modernities have had their own dialectics of struggle of instrumental rationality of the system and ambiguous communicational rationality of life-world.

In this struggle university has played a role of a leading institute that was weak in promotion of critical rationalization in traditional societies and strong in institutionalization of power that was undermining modernity goals of individual’s emancipation.

1.1 Introduction

The post-Soviet nations live in a peculiar time. This peculiarity is vested into a number of time-lapses, coexistence of past and new social life-forms in one contemporary event. Just a handful of examples from recent decade: the Cossacks, paramilitary strata of Russian stardom in XVII-XVIII centuries, patrolled Sochi Olympic games, and other Cossack-like groups defended Maidan parameter from special police forces in Kiev in 2014; Orthodox priests go to offices belonging to

newly appointed public officials to “take away the bad luck” of their predecessors in Moscow and Odessa; queues of Russian, Ukrainian and Georgian politicians to consult with wizards on future of their political projects; clan factions in Central-Asian parliaments; memory wars among Belarus, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia and Ukraine use historical argument as a legitimate one in public legal acts. Such retro-modern junctures show that the modernity in post-Soviet societies has reached the period when traditional life-forms are equally important phenomena of social life in spite of several centuries long Eastern European modernization.

In order to get answers how this peculiar—alternative—modernity came to existence, one needs to review the path of structural transformation of societies that parted with their traditional form of existence as a part of Russian Empire and/or Soviet Union. The same transformations were continued in the new independent nations after the collapse of Soviet Union. Every time big political project was collapsing, for the Ukrainians, the Russians and other peoples of the region there were a chance to constitute their state, to clearly divide public and private spheres, and to establish social institutions enabling self-realization of individuality. Yet every time Eastern European modernity somehow was leading to be different from the Western models and forms that it had attempted to copy. Neither Jürgen Habermas¹ nor Hannah Arendt² could have imagined that modernizing motivations can lead to anti-modern results. The promise of universal rights and civic freedoms in Eastern European revolutions was leading to decrease of individual liberties, dominance of collective values and increase of irrational politics.

How did it happen that Eastern European modernity is based on a permanent misuse of modernizing strives? How did it happen that modern Eastern European—the Poles, the Russians, the Ukrainians, and other peoples of the region—keep up to the repeating patterns of self-destructing contemporaneity? What is happening in our Eastern Europe, when a zeal for rationalization of management of social and economic processes leads to the establishment of regimes with rational instruments and irrational definition of aims? In this article I am trying to outline a possible answer and to demonstrate a special way of Eastern European/Russian/Soviet modernization path on the example of how a university, one of the core modernizing institutions, was functioning here. My major thesis is that, unlike in Western European context, university has played an ambivalent role in Eastern Europe: on the one hand, it has been a leading organization to copy, domesticate and redistribute critical rationality and scientific worldview among peoples living in Russian Empire and USSR, and, on the other hand, an institute of power, which has promulgated the mixture of modern and anti-modern values and practices.

1 See: Habermas J. *Strukturwandel der Öffentlichkeit*/Jurgem Habermas/. – Fr.a.Main: Suhrkamp, 1990. – 388 p.

2 See in particular: Arendt H. *On revolution* /Hannah Arendt/. – London: Penguin books, 1965. – P. 21 ff.

In order to prove this thesis in the paper, I will 1) examine key concepts which I will be using (modernity and modernities, modernization and so on); 2) point out the role of university in modernization processes; 3) describe the evolution of university model and the specific features of its impact on Modernity in the Russian Empire, the USSR and post-Soviet nations.

1.2 Multiple Modernities and Diversity of Traditions

Modernization means a complex of changes in cultural, social-economic, technical and political dimensions, thanks to which a society is no longer led by tradition and develops according to the future-oriented decisions. The situation in which societies where tradition does not play the guiding role is called modernity.

On a collective level, a break with traditional society order is introduced through rationalization, secularization and bureaucratization. Rationalization implies using of judgement based on consistent and uncontroversial arguments that are done by an individual, which will bare responsibility for it. As a result, Galileo's, Newton's, Leibnitz's and Bacon's prescriptions for rationalization as of "regulation of chaos" and "enlightenment of darkness" are exercised through repetitive and logically meaningful procedures. Rationalized world becomes more responsible and more manifold, demanding new forms of "industry of subject".³ Rationalization displays human freedom, and world rationalization needs people being able to appreciate freedom and act according to it. Secularization means forcing religious arguments out of public space; religion and its organized forms (church, parish, confession) become part of private space.⁴ Religion also ceases to be a decisive identity; religious tolerance becomes normal in modern society. Secularization is also an institutional change on a political level, where religion is not part of authorities any more.

Bureaucratization is a rationalization of practice used by authorities and based on notions of effective management of resources, responsible government, separation of powers and unity of political and law space. Responsible government has to take care of common wealth comprising all kinds of wealth for citizens (i.e. for individuals, whose freedom is determined by the sum of integral, rationally justified rights and responsibilities). Separation of powers sets competition among authorities with a view to providing a mutual control and guarantee of freedom for citizens. Finally, a unity of political and law space destroys traditional geography with "olden times" and "traditional freedoms", establishing an ideal notion of a country's space wholeness in view of a number of citizens' rights and responsibilities.

3 This term was introduced by M. Foucault, who described results of educational and scientific systems in a modern society. See: Foucault M. *Intellectuals and power* /Michelle Foucault/. – M.: Praxis, 2002. – C. 301 and further on.

4 Casanova J. Rethinking secularization: A global comparative perspective. In Casanova J. *Religion, globalization, and culture*. Leiden: Brill, 2007, pp. 101-120.

All the three main processes together structure every possible cooperation of people in a universal way in accordance with an interest and instrument of its defense: in such a way evolves public and private domain. Public domain regards interests, which fundamentally concern every member of society, and the private ones—interests, which demand respect, but which cannot be considered universal. Such structuring is a fundamental feature of a modern society.

On an individual level a break with cultural condition of society is introduced through autonomy of an individual, values of self-expression (or self-realization) and freedom of expression. Autonomy of an individual is an idea which considers individual free from external constraint; Kant and Hegel expose this idea in their own way, making “a free individual” to be a source of normativity. In a modernized society there were created systems of education as industries of producing individuals, capable of autonomy. Values of self-expression and freedom of expression are ideas that belong to leading principles of individual’s life in modern society. They exercise a considerable pressure on an individual, provoking him/her into being “him- or herself” or “escape from freedom”. The choice of the latter strategies leads to domination of different types of political systems, which either carry on with modernization, or wrap it up.

In this way modernity is a flowing, progressing condition of a society, which takes place as a transitional result of modernization. Modernity is a condition of post-traditional society. This condition is notable for its “transformativity” (Habermas⁵) and «fluidity» (Baumann⁶), i.e. adherence to permanent change. And the condition of *high modernity* is a period starting in the first decade of 20th century for the bigger part of world cultures.

Modernizing transformation takes place due to cultural and social institutes introducing rationalization of a life-world of tradition. To such institutes belong modern philosophy (a quest for the limits and sense of freedom and justice), science (use of rationality), bureaucracy (technology of governance), technology-industry (production of material goods and their surplus), and market economy (system of benefits and inducement to consume).

Taking into account the transformativity of modern society, modernity has its own history of radical changes. In philosophical, historical and sociological literature there are several acknowledged periodizations of the rise and spread of modernity. For the needs of this paper (namely, the evolution of modernity in Eastern Europe), I will be using the periodization proposed by Alain Touraine. He demonstrated the way a modern society has been changing according to a defining principle of substitution of the role, which tradition has played in an archaic society. It is a

5 Тут див. уже вказану книгу «Strukturwandel der Öffentlichkeit».

6 Baumann Z. Liquid Modernity /Zygmunt Bauman/. – Malden, MA: Polity Press, 2000. – P.1ff.

case of legitimacy: the first period of modernity was attributed to confessional and/or political form of collectivity (early modern religious wars and absolutism), later on sociality took the defining role over (capitalism and socialism), which led to emergence of industrial society, where individual's identity was not in need of collective source of her or his own identity for the first time⁷.

Despite the fact that modernity is an age of universal norms and values, which initially deny cultural bias towards these norms, historical embodiment of modernity differs through regions and epochs. For this reason a term of "multiple modernities" was introduced. Its author, Shmuel Eisenstadt, called so the condition of post-traditional societies, which acknowledge the autonomy of the subject, have specifically restricted the influence of tradition and created public structures. In so doing he established a protection from absolutization of universality, which interpreted any differences between modern societies outside Western world as false or deviant. As Eisenstadt used to argue, "Western models of modernity are not the only "authentic" models, even though they historically precede all the other ones".⁸

1.3 Modernization Travail of University

In times of modernity university takes on great importance. It acts as agent of socialization being in charge of rationalization of culture's life world. By contrast with other agents of socialization, a university simultaneously proves to be a place for creating forms of rationalization and producer of contents, as well as active institute for promulgating these forms and contents. In practice it means that university gains importance as a government institution, which is systematic and alternative to other government institutions in modern society.

As has already been shown above, structural transformation of modernity had led to a distinct division in public and private domains with their separate institutes and interests. Jürgen Habermas has demonstrated that the public space had played a key role in this transformation as it was the sphere, where political communication took place among the citizens with equal rights and outside of traditional social divisions.⁹ This space of acknowledged political and legal equality established the core of public sphere.

Ideas and concepts which lay at heart of public space and its political communication had their roots in a République des Lettres. This inconspicuous "republic of the literates" consisting of

7 Touraine A. A New Paradigm for Understanding Today's World / Alain Touraine/. – Cambridge: Polity, 2007. – 216 p. – P.3ff.

8 Eisenstadt, S. Multiple Modernities /Simon Eisenstadt/, in: Daedalus. – 2000. – Vol.129, N1. - 1-29 pp, - P.2-3.

9 Habermas writes of 'autonomous bourgeois sphere' (salons and clubs) where representatives of different classes were able to equally discuss common 'public issues': Habermas J. Strukturwandel der Öffentlichkeit/Jürgem Habermas/. – Fr.a.Main: Suhrkamp, 1990. – 388 p. – P. 34ff.

its own political, ideological, and epistemological parties (e.g. Leibnizians and Newtonians, sceptics and enthusiasts, dogmatics and critics), whose discussions were dedicated to forming and spreading ideals of Enlightenment, scientific rationality and critical prescriptions for social-political circumstances in traditional society. For salons and clubs of the 18th century to become places for promoting of publicity practice, ideas of right, civil liberties and responsible government had to be articulated and considered to be just.

Universities served as an important tool for producing and promulgating of these Enlightenment ideas. Yet university was created in the conditions of traditional society. University as an institute of traditional society was considerably constrained in the production of politically significant ideas. On the one hand, structures of traditional power (church, royal or imperial power and town community) acknowledged and granted a university's autonomy. On the other hand, this autonomy was not absolute, universities were frequently agents of additional legitimation of institutes of power—monarchies and/or religious leaders. However, a scientific knowledge and technology were born there as well.

A conservative nature of a traditional university imposed limits on natural philosophers and naturalists in 16-17th centuries, hence constant attempts to provide a scientific alternative to existing universities (e.g. royal scientific society, invisible college, Academy). At the same time, university structures remained very important in a structure of producing politically significant knowledge and the main organization of its promulgating (on a par with media).

Reforms of the Western European university coincided in time with reformation and counter-reformation. During the first confessional and absolutist era of social modernization universities were the subject of serious transformation. Struggle between governments and confessional organizations demanded more and more people for an emerging state bureaucracy, absolutism's propagandists, and activists in new church networks. Accordingly, there appeared new competitive systems of education for elites and common people. In the 17-18th centuries new attempts were undertaken to thoroughly re-establish universities for benefit of science, government and church. Homogeneity of university ambient disappears. Every experiment led to more unique models: confessional Halle university in Germany, governmental university in Uppsala or global network of Jesuit collegiums from Italy to Japan and Peru. As a result, there emerged new university environments promoting different but at the same time interrelated projects of modernity — educational, absolutist and conservative ones.

These experiments had different grade of promoting rationality and freedom ideals. Immanuel Kant criticized attempts to enslave university rationality in his age (18th century). Main

message of his “Argument of faculties” is to keep distance from external power centers, maintaining influence of reason on a society of intelligent human beings.¹⁰

However, a transition from absolutism to nationalism fostered nationalization of systems of education. New political systems were supported by Humboldtian reform of university. With universities being now financially supported by government, the resources for instrumental rationalization increased and scientific autonomy decreased. University became the main place for production of individuals belonging to nationalist modernity. It is exactly this model which made part of a toolkit of modernization models, which were introduced in other modernity projects around the globe—including the Russian imperial project that formed the Eastern European modernity landscape.

Accordingly, within alternative modernity projects, the different cultures could use modernization potential of universities for their own purposes. In many modern projects of the 19-20th centuries a connection between freedom and rationality was attacked by power institutes, and a university was one of the spaces of such ‘enslavement of mind’ and substitution of rational values.

Therefore, university is one of the key institutes, which played a key role in shaping of modern ideas for and introducing rationality into traditional cultures. Due to reforms in 17-19th centuries university became a global model of industry of modern human beings, subjects capable of participating in transformation and of controlling this transformation.

1.4. University and Fate of Modernities in the Russian Empire, the USSR and Post-Soviet Countries

In certain cultural zones modernity took place with the use of already existing modernization models (the ones that were elaborated in the cultures of the Western Europe). Since historically Western Europe turned out to be first in its break with traditional society, its models were often used as examples to follow. In particular, it was true for a university. Yet the resettlement of European models into new cultural grounds was determined by local cultural agents, their power dispositions and goals. Thanks to this choice, university has often played a contradictory role in view of modernization effect: on the one hand, it helped to foster the break with tradition in a given society and sped up local social development, and on the other hand, it was helping to decrease individual freedoms and to set control mechanisms over the expected end-results of Enlightenment. In the

¹⁰ Kant, I. *The Conflict of the Faculties*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1992.

Russian Imperial and Soviet contexts, university was mutating into anti-modernist institute with anti-Western agenda.

In cultures, where the break with tradition has started within the context of Russian empire, a university was simultaneously an agent for ‘disenchantment of the world’, and a source of anti-rationalizing strategies to produce ‘captive minds’. Elites of the Russian Empire borrowed the Western university model at the outset of the 19th century, during the reign of Alexander I. In spite of many models existing at the time in Western Europe,¹¹ it was Napoleon and Swedish (Upsala experiment) models that were widely introduced into the imperial administrative system. This model was built on government’s critical role in setting up agenda for universities, and making universities part of administration of the Empire. In 1803-4 reform Alexander I abandoned unsuccessful practice created by the Moscow university in 18th century, or by Kyiv-Mohyla Academy in 17th – 18th centuries, and covered entire Russian territory with academic regions administratively controlled by universities. Thus universities’ self-governance bodies mutated into parts of a big ministry of ‘Enlightenment’ while losing autonomy of the academic—scientific—corporation.

The paragon of the latter was an attempt to form ‘governmental university’ in Uppsala, which was actively being studied both in academic reforms of ‘liberal’ 1803 and of ‘conservative’ 1837. As a result, a new hybrid university model in Russia included the following features:

- 1) its founder was government (state);
- 2) government sets university management personnel and goals for university’s existence;
- 3) university autonomy is of little value for the corporation of academicians;
- 4) university is not a separate unit, it is regarded to be an integral part of Ministry for peoples’ education (*narodnogo prosveshchenia*), a special institute having a monopoly to produce modernity individuals;
- 5) hierarchy of tasks of a Russian university comprises of (in order of importance)
 - 1) administrative goal,
 - 2) socialization goals,
 - 3) educational goals, and to some extent
 - 4) scientific and research goals.

11 There were also some universities or university-like institutes that existed in Russian empire before 19th century. Their role in modernization is described later in this paper.

During later stages of modernization of societies that were ruled by Russian Empire in the 19th century, this model of university—‘governmental university’—survived and developed in the totalitarian period, and in the post-totalitarian period of the late USSR and in post-Soviet cultures.

By stating that a winning model of university in Eastern Europe and Western Eurasia—from Eastern Baltics to the Pacific Ocean—was a ‘governmental university’, I do not deny the existence of alternative university models in the societies that entered into modernity under—or continued their modernization under strong influence of—the Russian Empire. University as a cultural and social institute was borrowed by all these Eastern European cultures from two sources: the southern (Polish Jesuit) and the northern (German and Swedish) traditions of 18th century.

The Polish model of a university was based on the early modern reaction of traditional society towards rationalization of a life-world. Polish counter-reformation led to the spreading of contradictory practice of opposition to rationalization by establishing special educational institutes, which produced individuals ready to combine confessional Catholic loyalty with virtues of political bias of early modern man. Readiness of Jesuit collegiums for upbringing of active figures with strong loyalty to Catholic Church set an example for early modern Ukrainian and Russian educational experiments in 17th – 18th centuries. There, education was combined with constraints of critical thinking and enforcing loyalty towards authorities. Long-lasting existence of Kyiv-Mohyla academy, which was an Orthodox replica of the Jesuit college, provided cadres for the Russian empire and coined a model of an educational institute that combined political and confessional functionalities to support the case of the Empire. It was a model which simultaneously supported the political modernization of the Empire, and yet it was limiting the political and scholarly rationality.

The Northern way of university model transfer used the examples of reformed universities of Germany (Halle) and Sweden (Uppsala) in 18th century. The traditional model of Moscow University (that was modelled according to early Western university reforms) turned out to be unsuccessful: it had a very limited impact upon elites’ formation in the 18th century Russia. The academic experiments in the 19th century were borrowing from later Western European models of ‘governmental university’. These universities were a sort of hybrids of an autonomous institute responsible for producing, transmitting, keeping and spreading of knowledge and of governmental institution.

In the first half of 19th century Russian imperial authorities created a stable model of a university as a place for fusion of normative (academic freedom) and power (administrative unit, a place for producing people of counter-Enlightenment) practices. Having borrowed a university as a

main form of educational and scientific institute, having applied it to experience of Orthodox interpretation in Jesuit collegiums and having added some aspects of Napoleon's and Humboldt's university models, reform ideologists of Alexander's I and Nicolas' I established a stable cultural institute which exercised

- practice of technical modernization, and
- spread of cultural forms of 'captive mind' in the form of imperialism, 'class consciousness' (in Soviet times) and 'scientific nationalism' (in post-Soviet times).

University in imperial times was dysfunctional in view of transformational needs of modernization. It combined elements of academic autonomy (an alternative to power and traditional) with strong core of participation in power relations as part of government (a center for administrative decision-making). As a result, university became an institute of growing irrational practice and values, and only in the case of its inappropriate functioning rationalized cultural world of the peoples ruled by the Empire.

In times of Russian Empire's collapse and competition of revolutionary socialist and nationalist projects (1917 – 1923), the model of governmental university survived, evolved, and played a crucial role for the USSR modernization path. First features of 'governmental university' appear in systematization of education under Stalin in 1933 – 1935. Soviet university became a place for exerting control over social and humanities' studies, an institute for producing and replication of a totalitarian man. It returned to its scientific function—including creation of new technologies and fundamental science research—much later and in connection to the need to compete with the West. In the post-Stalin period, a Soviet university carried on with the logic of development of 'governmental university', enforced by the break between education and science in the 1960-s (by allocating the conduction of researches to the responsibility of Academy for Science, by turning universities into mass institutions of education and 'proletarian upbringing'). University in the USSR was further on considered to be a governmental body, not an enterprise of scientists and scholars with the scientific aims. It became a place to control humanities and social sciences, promulgating values of technical modernization alongside with the uncritical thinking.

Renewal of 'governmental university' also took place after the fall of the USSR. After a short period of freedom and chaos, post-Soviet universities turned into de facto departments of Ministry of education that controls content of education, academic cadres and their careers, and universities' budgets. Possibilities for 'private' universities development were limited by legal over-regulation. Modest autonomy of universities in 1990-s was slowly turning into feudalism of rectors, who participated in the governance of post-Soviet corporation named 'Ministry of education and

science' paying for their power to the Center with revival of censorship and propaganda in the educational institutions. These corporations grew up in all Eastern European nations and played important role in creation of loyal cadres for power institutions. However, their role in reproduction of science and scholarship was minimal and dependent on Western scientific centers. Practice and values which are spread through networks of post-Soviet Ministries of education promote a deficient modernization and inspire de-modernization in Ukraine, Russia and Belorussia.